

N° FIELD ID	Site	Date of Collection	Date of extraction	PCR Pancoronavirus	PCR Pan Astrovirus
MAGBT01	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT02	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT03	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT04	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT05	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT06	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT07	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT08	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT09	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	+
MAGBT10	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT11	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT12	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT13	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT14	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT15	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT16	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
MAGBT17	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
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MAGBT19	Magweto cave	17/9/20	12/10/20	-	-
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MAGBT26	Magweto cave	17/9/20	13/10/20	-	-
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MAGBT30	Magweto cave	17/9/20	13/10/20	-	-
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MAGBT32	Magweto cave	17/9/20	13/10/20	-	-
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MAGBT39	Magweto cave	17/9/20	13/10/20	-	-
MAGBT40	Magweto cave	17/9/20	13/10/20	-	-
MAGBT41	Magweto cave	17/9/20	13/10/20	-	-
MAGBT42	Magweto cave	17/9/20	13/10/20	-	-
MAGBT43	Magweto cave	17/9/20	13/10/20	-	-
MAGBT44	Magweto cave	17/9/20	13/10/20	-	-
MAGBT45	Magweto cave	17/9/20	13/10/20	-	-
MAGBT46	Magweto cave	17/9/20	13/10/20	-	-

MAGBT47	Magweto cave	17/9/20	13/10/20	-	-
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MAGBT120	Magweto cave	17/9/20	28/10/20	-	-
MAGBT121	Magweto cave	17/9/20	28/10/20	+	-
MAGBT122	Magweto cave	17/9/20	28/10/20	-	-
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MAGBT144	Magweto cave	17/9/20	28/10/20	-	-
MAGBT145	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
MAGBT146	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	+
MAGBT147	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
MAGBT148	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
MAGBT149	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
MAGBT150	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
MAGBT151	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	+
MAGBT152	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
MAGBT153	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
MAGBT154	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
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MAGBT161	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
MAGBT162	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
MAGBT163	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	+
MAGBT164	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
MAGBT165	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
MAGBT166	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
MAGBT167	Magweto cave	17/9/20	29/10/20	-	-
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MAGBT170	Magweto cave	17/9/20	10/11/20	-	-
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MAGBT194	Magweto cave	17/9/20	11/11/20	-	-
MAGBT195	Magweto cave	17/9/20	11/11/20	-	-
MAGBT196	Magweto cave	17/9/20	11/11/20	-	-
MAGBT197	Magweto cave	17/9/20	11/11/20	-	+
MAGBT198	Magweto cave	17/9/20	11/11/20	-	+
MAGBT199	Magweto cave	17/9/20	11/11/20	-	-
MAGBT200	Magweto cave	17/9/20	11/11/20	-	-
MAGBT201	Magweto cave	17/9/20	11/11/20	-	-
MAGBT202	Magweto cave	17/9/20	11/11/20	-	+
MAGBT203	Magweto cave	17/9/20	11/11/20	-	-
MAGBT204	Magweto cave	17/9/20	11/11/20	-	-
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MAGBT213	Magweto cave	17/9/20	11/11/20	-	-
MAGBT214	Magweto cave	17/9/20	11/11/20	+	-
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MAGBT246	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	-	-
MAGBT247	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	-	+
MAGBT248	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	-	-
MAGBT249	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	-	-
MAGBT250	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	+	+
MAGBT251	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	-	+
MAGBT252	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	-	-
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MAGBT255	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	-	-
MAGBT256	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	-	+
MAGBT257	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	-	-
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MAGBT260	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	-	-
MAGBT261	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	+	-
MAGBT262	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	-	-
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MAGBT264	Magweto cave	18/9/20	18/11/20	-	-
MAGBT265	Magweto cave	18/9/20	19/11/20	+	-
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MAGBT281	Magweto cave	18/9/20	19/11/20	-	+
MAGBT282	Magweto cave	18/9/20	19/11/20	-	-
MAGBT283	Magweto cave	18/9/20	19/11/20	-	-
MAGBT284	Magweto cave	18/9/20	19/11/20	-	-
MAGBT285	Magweto cave	18/9/20	19/11/20	-	-
MAGBT286	Magweto cave	18/9/20	19/11/20	-	-

MAGBT287	Magweto cave	18/9/20	19/11/20	-	-
MAGBT288	Magweto cave	18/9/20	19/11/20	+	-
MAGBT289	Magweto cave	18/9/20	27/11/20	-	+
MAGBT290	Magweto cave	18/9/20	27/11/20	-	-
MAGBT291	Magweto cave	18/9/20	27/11/20	-	-
MAGBT292	Magweto cave	18/9/20	27/11/20	-	+
MAGBT293	Magweto cave	18/9/20	27/11/20	-	+
MAGBT294	Magweto cave	18/9/20	27/11/20	-	-
MAGBT295	Magweto cave	18/9/20	27/11/20	-	-
MAGBT296	Magweto cave	18/9/20	27/11/20	-	-
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MAGBT312	Magweto cave	18/9/20	2/12/20	-	-
MAGBT313	Magweto cave	18/9/20	2/12/20	-	-
MAGBT314	Magweto cave	18/9/20	2/12/20	-	-
MAGBT315	Magweto cave	18/9/20	2/12/20	-	-
MAGBT316	Magweto cave	18/9/20	2/12/20	-	-
MAGBT317	Magweto cave	18/9/20	2/12/20	-	-
MAGBT318	Magweto cave	18/9/20	2/12/20	-	-
MAGBT319	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	-
MAGBT320	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	-
MAGBT321	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	-
MAGBT322	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	+
MAGBT323	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	-
MAGBT324	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	-
MAGBT325	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	-
MAGBT326	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	-
MAGBT327	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	-
MAGBT328	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	-
MAGBT329	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	-
MAGBT330	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	-
MAGBT331	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	-
MAGBT332	Magweto cave	18/9/20	1/12/20	-	-
MAGBT333	Magweto cave	18/9/20	2/12/20	-	-
MAGBT334	Magweto cave	18/9/20	2/12/20	-	-

MAGBT335	Magweto cave	18/9/20	2/12/20	-	-
MAGBT336	Magweto cave	18/9/20	2/12/20	-	-
MAGBT337	Magweto cave	18/9/20	2/12/20	-	+
MAGBT338	Magweto cave	18/9/20	3/12/20	-	-
MAGBT339	Magweto cave	18/9/20	3/12/20	-	-
MAGBT340	Magweto cave	18/9/20	3/12/20	-	-
MAGBT341	Magweto cave	18/9/20	3/12/20	-	-
MAGBT342	Magweto cave	18/9/20	3/12/20	-	-
MAGBT343	Magweto cave	18/9/20	3/12/20	-	-
MAGBT344	Magweto cave	18/9/20	3/12/20	-	-
MAGBT345	Magweto cave	18/9/20	3/12/20	-	-
MAGBT346	Magweto cave	18/9/20	3/12/20	-	-
MAGBT347	Magweto cave	18/9/20	3/12/20	-	-
MAGBT348	Magweto cave	18/9/20	3/12/20	-	-
MAGBT349	Magweto cave	20/10/20	3/12/20	-	-
MAGBT350	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	+
MAGBT351	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT352	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	+
MAGBT353	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT354	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT355	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT356	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT357	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT358	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT359	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT360	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	+	-
MAGBT361	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT362	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	+
MAGBT363	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	+
MAGBT364	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT365	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT366	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	+	-
MAGBT367	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT368	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	+
MAGBT369	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	+
MAGBT370	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	+
MAGBT371	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT372	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT373	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	+
MAGBT374	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT375	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	+
MAGBT376	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT377	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT378	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT379	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT380	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT381	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT382	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-

MAGBT383	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT384	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT385	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT386	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	+
MAGBT387	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT388	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	+	-
MAGBT389	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT390	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT391	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT392	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT393	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	+	-
MAGBT394	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT395	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT396	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	+
MAGBT397	Magweto cave	20/10/20	31/03/21	-	-
MAGBT398	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT399	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT400	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT401	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT402	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	+
MAGBT403	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	+
MAGBT404	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	+	-
MAGBT405	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT406	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT407	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT408	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT409	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT410	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	+	+
MAGBT411	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT412	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT413	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT414	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT415	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT416	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT417	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT418	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT419	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	+
MAGBT420	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT421	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT422	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	+
MAGBT423	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	+	-
MAGBT424	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	+	+
MAGBT425	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT426	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT427	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	+	-
MAGBT428	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT429	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	+
MAGBT430	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-

MAGBT431	Magweto cave	20/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT432	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT433	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/6/21	-	-
MAGBT434	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT435	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT436	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT437	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT438	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT439	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT440	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT441	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT442	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	+
MAGBT443	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT444	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT445	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	+	-
MAGBT446	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT447	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT448	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT449	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT450	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT451	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT452	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT453	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT454	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT455	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT456	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT457	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT458	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT459	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT460	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT461	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	+
MAGBT462	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT463	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	+
MAGBT464	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT465	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT466	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT467	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT468	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT469	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT470	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT471	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT472	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT473	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT474	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT475	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT476	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT477	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT478	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-

MAGBT479	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT480	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT481	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	+
MAGBT482	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT483	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	+	-
MAGBT484	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT485	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT486	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT487	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT488	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT489	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT490	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	+
MAGBT491	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT492	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT493	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT494	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT495	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	+
MAGBT496	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	+
MAGBT497	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT498	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT499	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT500	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT501	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT502	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT503	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT504	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	+
MAGBT505	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT506	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	+
MAGBT507	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT508	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT509	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT510	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT511	Magweto cave	21/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT512	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT513	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT514	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT515	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT516	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	+
MAGBT517	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT518	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT519	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT520	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT521	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT522	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT523	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT524	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT525	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	+
MAGBT526	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-

MAGBT527	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	+
MAGBT528	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT529	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/7/21	-	-
MAGBT530	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT531	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT532	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT533	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT534	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT535	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT536	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT537	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT538	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT539	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT540	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT541	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT542	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT543	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT544	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT545	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT546	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT547	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT548	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	+
MAGBT549	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	+
MAGBT550	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT551	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT552	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT553	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT554	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT555	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT556	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	+
MAGBT557	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	-
MAGBT558	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	-
MAGBT559	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT560	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	-
MAGBT561	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	-
MAGBT562	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	-
MAGBT563	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT564	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT565	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT566	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	-
MAGBT567	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT568	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT569	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT570	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT571	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT572	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	-
MAGBT573	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT574	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-

MAGBT575	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	-
MAGBT576	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT577	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	+
MAGBT578	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT579	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT580	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	+
MAGBT581	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT582	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT583	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	-
MAGBT584	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT585	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT586	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT587	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT588	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT589	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT590	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT591	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT592	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT593	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	-
MAGBT594	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT595	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT596	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	+	-
MAGBT597	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT598	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT599	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT600	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT601	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT602	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT603	Magweto cave	22/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT604	Magweto cave	23/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT605	Magweto cave	24/10/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT606	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT607	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT608	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT609	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT610	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT611	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT612	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT613	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT614	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT615	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT616	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT617	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT618	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT619	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT620	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT621	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	+
MAGBT622	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	+

MAGBT623	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT624	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT625	Magweto cave	25/11/20	4/8/21	-	-
MAGBT626	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT627	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT628	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT629	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT630	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT631	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT632	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT633	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT634	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT635	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT636	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT637	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT638	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT639	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT640	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT641	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT642	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT643	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT644	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT645	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT646	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT647	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT648	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT649	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT650	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT651	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT652	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT653	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	+	+
MAGBT654	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT655	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT656	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT657	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT658	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT659	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT660	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT661	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT662	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT663	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT664	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT665	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT666	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT667	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT668	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT669	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT670	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-

MAGBT671	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT672	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT673	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT674	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT675	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT676	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT677	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT678	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT679	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT680	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT681	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT682	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT683	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT684	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT685	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT686	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT687	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT688	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT689	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT690	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT691	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT692	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT693	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT694	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT695	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT696	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT697	Magweto cave	25/11/20	13/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT698	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT699	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT700	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT701	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT702	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT703	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT704	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT705	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT706	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT707	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT708	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT709	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT710	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT711	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT712	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT713	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT714	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	+	+
MAGBT715	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT716	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT717	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT718	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-

MAGBT767	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT768	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT769	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT770	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT771	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT772	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT773	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT774	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT775	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT776	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT777	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT778	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	+	+
MAGBT779	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT780	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT781	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT782	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT783	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT784	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT785	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT786	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT787	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT788	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT789	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT790	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT791	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT792	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT793	Magweto cave	25/11/20	14/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT794	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT795	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT796	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT797	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT798	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT799	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT800	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT801	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT802	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT803	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT804	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT805	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT806	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT807	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT808	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT809	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT810	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT811	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT812	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT813	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT814	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-

MAGBT815	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT816	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT817	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT818	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT819	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT820	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT821	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT822	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT823	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT824	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT825	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT826	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT827	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT828	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT829	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT830	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT831	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT832	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT833	Magweto cave	25/11/20	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT834	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT835	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT837	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT838	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT839	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT840	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT841	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT842	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT843	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT844	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT845	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT846	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT847	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT848	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT849	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT850	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	+	+
MAGBT851	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT852	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT853	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT854	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT855	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT856	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT857	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT858	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT859	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	+	+
MAGBT860	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT861	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT862	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	+
MAGBT863	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	+	-

MAGBT864	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	+	+
MAGBT865	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	+	-
MAGBT866	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/04/2021	-	-
MAGBT867	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT868	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT869	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT870	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	+
MAGBT871	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT872	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT873	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	-
MAGBT874	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT875	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT876	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	-
MAGBT877	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	-
MAGBT878	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT879	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT880	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	-
MAGBT881	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT882	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	+
MAGBT883	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	+
MAGBT884	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT885	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	+
MAGBT886	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	-
MAGBT887	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	-
MAGBT888	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT889	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	-
MAGBT890	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT891	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT892	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT893	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT894	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT895	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT896	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT897	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	-
MAGBT898	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	-
MAGBT899	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	-
MAGBT900	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT901	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT902	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT903	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT904	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	+
MAGBT905	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	-
MAGBT906	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	-
MAGBT907	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	-
MAGBT908	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT909	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT910	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT911	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-

MAGBT912	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	-	-
MAGBT913	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	+
MAGBT914	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/8/21	+	
MAGBT915	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	+
MAGBT916	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT917	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT918	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT919	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT920	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT921	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT922	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT923	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT924	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT925	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT926	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT927	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT928	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT929	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT930	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21		+
MAGBT931	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT932	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT933	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT934	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT935	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT936	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	+
MAGBT937	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT938	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	+
MAGBT939	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT940	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	+
MAGBT941	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT942	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT943	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	+
MAGBT944	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT945	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT946	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT947	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT948	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT949	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT950	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT951	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	+
MAGBT952	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT953	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT954	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT955	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT956	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT957	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	+
MAGBT958	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	+
MAGBT959	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-

MAGBT960	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	+
MAGBT961	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT962	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT963	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	+	-
MAGBT964	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/10/21	-	-
MAGBT965	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT966	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	+
MAGBT967	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	+
MAGBT968	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT969	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT970	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT971	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT972	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT973	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	+
MAGBT974	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT975	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	-
MAGBT976	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	-
MAGBT977	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	+
MAGBT978	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	-
MAGBT979	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT980	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	+
MAGBT981	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	-
MAGBT982	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	-
MAGBT983	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT984	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	+
MAGBT985	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	-
MAGBT986	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT987	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	+
MAGBT988	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	+
MAGBT989	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21		-
MAGBT990	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	-
MAGBT991	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT992	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	+
MAGBT993	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	+
MAGBT995	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	-
MAGBT996	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	+
MAGBT997	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	+
MAGBT998	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT999	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT1000	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	-
MAGBT1001	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	-
MAGBT1002	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	+	-
MAGBT1003	Magweto cave	4/3/21	6/11/21	-	-
MAGBT1004	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1005	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1006	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1007	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1008	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	+	-

MAGBT1009	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1010	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1011	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1012	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1013	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1014	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1015	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1016	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1017 (1)	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1017 (2)	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1018	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1019	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1020	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1021	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1022	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1023	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1024	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1025	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1026	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1027	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1028	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1029	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1030	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1031	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1032	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1033	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1034	Magweto cave	4/3/21	14/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1035	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1036	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1037	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1038	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1039	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1040	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1041	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1042	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1043	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1044	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1045	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1046	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1047	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1048	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1049	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1050	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1051	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1052	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1053	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1054	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1055	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	+	-

MAGBT1056	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1057	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1058	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1059	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1060	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1061	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1062	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1063	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1064	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1065	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1066	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	+	+
MAGBT1067	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1068	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1069	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1070	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1071	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	+	+
MAGBT1072	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1073	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1074	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1075	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1076	Magweto cave	4/3/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1077	Magweto cave	12/4/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1078	Magweto cave	12/4/21	15/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1079	Magweto cave	12/4/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1080	Magweto cave	12/4/21	15/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1081	Magweto cave	12/4/21	15/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1082	Magweto cave	12/4/21	15/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1083	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1084	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1085 (1)	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1085 (2)	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1086	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1087	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1088	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1089	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1090	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1091	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1092	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1093	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1094	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1095	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1096	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1097	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1098	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1099	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1100	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1101	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1112	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-

MAGBT1113	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1114	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1115	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1116	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1117	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1118	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1119	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1120	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1121	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1122	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1123	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1124	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1125	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1126	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1127	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1128	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1129	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1130	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1131	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1132	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1133	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1134	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1135	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1136	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1137	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1138	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1139	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1140	Magweto cave	12/4/21	16/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1141	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1142	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1143	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1144	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1145	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1146	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1147	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1148	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1149	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1150	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1151	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1152	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1153	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1154	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1155	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1156	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1157	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1158	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1159	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1160	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-

MAGBT1161	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1162	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1163	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1164	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1165	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1166	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1167	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1168	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1169	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1170	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1171	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1172	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1173	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1174	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1175	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1176	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1177	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1178	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1179	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	+	+
MAGBT1180	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1181	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1182	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1183	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1184	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1185	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1186	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1187	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1188	Magweto cave	12/4/21	17/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1189	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1190	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1191	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1192	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1193	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1194	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1195	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1196	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1197	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1198	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1199	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1200	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1201	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1202	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1203	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1204	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1205	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1206	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1207	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1208	Magweto cave	12/4/21	21/06/2021	-	-

MAGBT1257	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1258	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1259	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1260	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1261	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1262	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1263	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1264	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1265	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1266	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1267	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1268	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1269	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1270	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1271	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1272	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1273	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1274	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1275	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1276	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1277	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1278	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1279	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1280	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1281	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1282	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1283	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1284	Magweto cave	12/4/21	22/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1285	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1286	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1287	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	+
MAGBT1288	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1289	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1290	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1291	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1292	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1293	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1294	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	+
MAGBT1295	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1296	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1297	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1298	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1299	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1300	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1301	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1302	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1303	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1304	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	-

MAGBT1305	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1306	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1307	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1308	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1309	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1310	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1311	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1312	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1313	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1314	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1315	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1316	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1317	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	+
MAGBT1318	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1319	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	+
MAGBT1320	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1321	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1322	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1323	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1324	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1325	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1326	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1327	Magweto cave	12/4/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1328	Magweto cave	3/6/21	23/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1329	Magweto cave	3/6/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1330	Magweto cave	3/6/21	23/06/2021	-	-
MAGBT1331	Magweto cave	3/6/21	23/06/2021	-	+
MAGBT1332	Magweto cave	3/6/21	23/06/2021	+	-
MAGBT1333	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1334	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1335	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1336	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1337	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1337 (2)	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1338	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1339	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1340	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1341	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1342	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1343	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1344	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1345	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1346	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1347	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1348	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1349	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1350	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1351	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-

MAGBT1352	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	+	-
MAGBT1353	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1354	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1355	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1356	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1357	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1358	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1359	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1360	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1361	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	+	-
MAGBT1362	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1363	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1364	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	+	-
MAGBT1365	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	+	-
MAGBT1366	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1367	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1368	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1369	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1370	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1371	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1372	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1373	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	+	+
MAGBT1374	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1375	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	+	-
MAGBT1376	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1377	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1378	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1379	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1380	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1381	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1382	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1383	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	+	-
MAGBT1384	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1385	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1386	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1387	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1388	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1389	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1390	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1391	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1392	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1393	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1394	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1395	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1396	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1397	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1398	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1399	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+

MAGBT1400	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1401	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1402	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1403	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	+	-
MAGBT1404	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1405	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1406	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1407	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1408	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1409	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1410	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	+	-
MAGBT1411	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1412	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1413	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1414	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1415	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1416	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1417	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1418	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1419	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1420	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1421	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1422	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1423	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1424	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1425	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1426	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1427	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1428	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1429	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1430	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1431	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1432	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1433	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1434	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1435	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1436	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1437	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1438	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1439	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1440	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1441	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1442	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1443	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1444	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1445	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1446	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1447	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-

MAGBT1448	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1449	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1450	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1451	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	+	-
MAGBT1452	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1453	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1454	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1455	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1456	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1457	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1458	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1459	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1460	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1461	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1462	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1463	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1464	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1465	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1466	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1467	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1468	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	+
MAGBT1469	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1470	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1471	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1472	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1473	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1474	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1475	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/2/21	-	-
MAGBT1476	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1477	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1478	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1479	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1480	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1481	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1482	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1483	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	+
MAGBT1484	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1485	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1486	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1487	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	+	-
MAGBT1488	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	+
MAGBT1489	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1490	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	+
MAGBT1491	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1492	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	+
MAGBT1493	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	+
MAGBT1494	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1495	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-

MAGBT1496	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1497	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1498	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	+
MAGBT1499	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1500	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1501	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	+	-
MAGBT1502	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1503	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1504	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	+
MAGBT1505	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1506	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	+
MAGBT1507	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1508	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1509	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1510	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1511	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1512	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1513	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1514	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1515	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	+	-
MAGBT1516	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	+	+
MAGBT1517	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	+
MAGBT1518	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1519	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1520	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1521	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	+	-
MAGBT1522	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	-
MAGBT1523	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/6/21	-	+
MAGBT1524	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1525	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1526	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1527	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1528	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1529	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+
MAGBT1530	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+
MAGBT1531	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1532	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+
MAGBT1533	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1534	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1535	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1536	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1537	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1538	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+
MAGBT1540	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1541	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+
MAGBT1542	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1543	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+
MAGBT1544	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-

MAGBT1545	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1546	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+
MAGBT1547	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1548	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1549	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+
MAGBT1550	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+
MAGBT1551	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1552	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+
MAGBT1553	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1554	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1555	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1556	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1557	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1558	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+
MAGBT1559	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	
MAGBT1560	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	+	+
MAGBT1561	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1562	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1563	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1564	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1565	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1566	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+
MAGBT1567	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+
MAGBT1568	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	-
MAGBT1569	Magweto cave	3/6/21	7/7/21	-	+

N° FIELD ID	Site	Date of Collection	Date of extraction	PCR	PCR Pan
				Pancoronavirus	Astrovirus
CHIBTID001	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID002	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID003	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID004	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID005	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID006	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID007	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID008	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID009	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID010	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID011	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID012	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID013	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID014	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID015	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID016	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID017	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID018	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID019	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID020	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID021	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID022	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID023	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID024	Chirundu	20/8/20	7/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID025	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID026	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID027	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID028	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID029	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	+	-
CHIBTID030	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID031	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID032	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID033	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID034	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID035	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID036	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID037	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID038	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID039	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID040	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID041	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID042	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID043	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	+	-
CHIBTID044	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID045	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID046	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-

CHIBTID047	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID048	Chirundu	20/8/20	8/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID049	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID050	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID051	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID052	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID053	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	+	-
CHIBTID054	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID055	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID056	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID057	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID058	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID059	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID060	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID061	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID062	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID063	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID064	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID065	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID066	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID067	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID068	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID069	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID070	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID071	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID072	Chirundu	20/8/20	9/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID073	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID074	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID075	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID076	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID077	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID078	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID079	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
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CHIBTID082	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID083	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID084	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID085	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
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CHIBTID087	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
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CHIBTID089	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
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CHIBTID091	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID092	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID093	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID094	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-

CHIBTID095	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID096	Chirundu	20/8/20	10/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID097	Chirundu	20/8/20	14/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID098	Chirundu	20/8/20	14/9/20	-	-
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CHIBTID101	Chirundu	21/8/20	14/9/20	-	-
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CHIBTID114	Chirundu	21/8/20	14/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID115	Chirundu	21/8/20	14/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID116	Chirundu	21/8/20	14/9/20	-	-
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CHIBTID121	Chirundu	21/8/20	24/9/20	-	-
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CHIBTID135	Chirundu	21/8/20	24/9/20	+	-
CHIBTID136	Chirundu	21/8/20	24/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID137	Chirundu	21/8/20	24/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID138	Chirundu	21/8/20	24/9/20	+	-
CHIBTID139	Chirundu	21/8/20	24/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID140	Chirundu	21/8/20	24/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID141	Chirundu	21/8/20	24/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID142	Chirundu	21/8/20	24/9/20	-	-

CHIBTID143	Chirundu	21/8/20	24/9/20	+	-
CHIBTID144	Chirundu	21/8/20	24/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID145	Chirundu	21/8/20	25/9/20	-	-
CHIBTID146	Chirundu	21/8/20	25/9/20	-	-
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CHIBTID153	Chirundu	21/8/20	25/9/20	+	-
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CHIBTID190	Chirundu	1/10/20	18/01/2021	-	-

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CHIBTID274	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	+	-
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CHIBTID276	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID277	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
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CHIBTID282	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID283	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID284	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID285	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID286	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-

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CHIBTID288	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID289	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID290	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID291	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID292	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	+	-
CHIBTID293	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID294	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID295	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
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CHIBTID297	Chirundu	1/10/20	26/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID298	Chirundu	1/10/20	27/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID299	Chirundu	1/10/20	27/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID300	Chirundu	1/10/20	27/01/2021	-	-
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CHIBTID303	Chirundu	1/10/20	27/01/2021	-	-
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CHIBTID307	Chirundu	2/10/20	27/01/2021	-	-
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CHIBTID327	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID328	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID329	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	+	-
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CHIBTID332	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID333	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID334	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	-	-

CHIBTID335	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID336	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID337	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID338	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID339	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	-	-
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CHIBTID342	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	-	-
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CHIBTID347	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID348	Chirundu	2/10/20	29/01/2021	-	-
CHIBTID349	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID350	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID351	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID352	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID353	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID354	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID355	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID356	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID357	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID358	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID359	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID360	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID361	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID362	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID363	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID364	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID365	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID366	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID367	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	+
CHIBTID368	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID369	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID370	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID371	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/1/21	-	-
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CHIBTID379	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID380	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID381	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID382	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-

CHIBTID383	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID384	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID385	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID386	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID387	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID388	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID389	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID390	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID391	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID392	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID393	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID394	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID395	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID396	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID397	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID398	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID399	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	+	-
CHIBTID400	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID401	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID402	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID403	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID404	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID405	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID406	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID407	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID408	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID409	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID410	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID411	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID412	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID413	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID414	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID415	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID416	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID417	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID418	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID419	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID420	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID421	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID422	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID423	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID424	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID425	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID426	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID427	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID428	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID429	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID430	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-

CHIBTID431	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID432	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID433	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID434	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID435	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID436	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID437	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID438	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID439	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID440	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID441	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID442	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID443	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID444	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID445	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID446	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID447	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID448	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID449	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID450	Chirundu	2/10/20	2/10/21	-	+
CHIBTID451	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID452	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID453	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID454	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/10/21	-	-
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CHIBTID461	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID462	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID463	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID464	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/10/21	-	-
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CHIBTID466	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID467	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID468	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/10/21	-	-
CHIBTID469	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/11/21	-	-
CHIBTID470	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/11/21	-	-
CHIBTID471	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/11/21	-	-
CHIBTID472	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/11/21	-	-
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CHIBTID475	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/11/21	-	-
CHIBTID476	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/11/21	-	-
CHIBTID477	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/11/21	-	-
CHIBTID478	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/11/21	-	-

CHIBTID479	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/11/21	-	-
CHIBTID480	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/11/21	-	-
CHIBTID481	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/11/21	-	-
CHIBTID482	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/11/21	-	-
CHIBTID483	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/11/21	-	-
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CHIBTID497	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID498	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/12/21	-	-
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CHIBTID507	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID508	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID509	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID510	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID511	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/12/21	-	-
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CHIBTID516	Chirundu	5/11/20	2/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID517	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID518	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID519	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID520	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID521	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
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CHIBTID523	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID524	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID525	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID526	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-

CHIBTID527	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID528	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID529	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID530	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	+	-
CHIBTID531	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID532	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID533	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID534	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID535	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID536	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID537	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID538	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	+	-
CHIBTID539	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID540	Chirundu	5/11/20	24/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID541	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID542	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID543	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID544	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID545	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID546	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID547	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID548	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID549	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID550	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID551	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID552	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID553	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID554	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID555	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID556	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID557	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID558	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID559	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID560	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID561	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID562	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID563	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID564	Chirundu	5/11/20	25/02/2021	-	-
CHIBTID565	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	+	-
CHIBTID566	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID567	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID568	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID569	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID570	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID571	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID572	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID573	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID574	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-

CHIBTID575	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	+	-
CHIBTID576	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID577	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID578	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID579	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID580	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID581	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID582	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID583	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID584	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID585	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID586	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID587	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID588	Chirundu	5/11/20	1/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID589	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID590	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID591	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID592	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID593	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID594	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	+	+
CHIBTID595	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID596	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID597	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID598	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID599	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID600	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID601	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID602	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID603	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID604	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID605	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID606	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID607	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID608	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID609	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID610	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID611	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID612	Chirundu	5/11/20	22/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID613	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID614	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID615	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID616	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID617	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID618	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID619	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID620	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID621	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID622	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-

CHIBTID623	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID624	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID625	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID626	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID627	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID628	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID629	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID630	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID631	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID632	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID633	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID634	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID635	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID636	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID637	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID638	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID639	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	+
CHIBTID640	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID641	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID642	Chirundu	5/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID643	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID644	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID645	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID646	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID647	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID648	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID649	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID650	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID651	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID652	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID653	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID654	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID655	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID656	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID657	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID658	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID659	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID660	Chirundu	6/11/20	23/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID661	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID662	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID663	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID664	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID665	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID666	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID667	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID668	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID669	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID670	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-

CHIBTID671	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID672	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID673	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID674	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID675	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID676	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID677	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID678	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID679	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID680	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	+	+
CHIBTID681	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID682	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID683	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID684	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID685	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID686	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID687	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID688	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID689	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID690	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID691	Chirundu	6/11/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID692	Chirundu	16/12/20	30/03/2021	-	-
CHIBTID693	Chirundu	16/12/20	30/03/2021	+	-
CHIBTID694	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID695	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID696	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID697	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID698	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID699	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID700	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID701	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID702	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID703	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID704	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID705	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID706	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID707	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID708	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID709	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID710	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID711	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID712	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID713	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID714	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID715	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID716	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID717	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID718	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-

CHIBTID719	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID720	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID721	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID722	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID723	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID724	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID725	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID726	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID727	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID728	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID729	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID730	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID731	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID732	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID733	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID734	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID735	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID736	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID737	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID738	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID739	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID740	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID741	Chirundu	16/12/20	20/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID742	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID743	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID744	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID745	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID746	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID747	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID748	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID749	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID750	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID751	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID752	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID753	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID754	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID755	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID756	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID757	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID758	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID759	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID760	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID761	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID762	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID763	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID764	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID765	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID766	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-

CHIBTID767	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID768	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID769	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID770	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID771	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID772	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID773	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID774	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID775	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID776	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID777	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID778	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID779	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID780	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID781	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID782	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID783	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID784	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID785	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID786	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID787	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID788	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID789	Chirundu	16/12/20	21/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID790	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID791	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID792	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID793	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID794	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID795	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID796	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID797	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID798	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID799	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID800	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID801	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID802	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID803	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID804	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID805	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID806	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID807	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID808	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID809	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID810	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID811	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID812	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID813	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID814	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID815	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID816	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID817	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-

CHIBTID818	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID819	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID820	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID821	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID822	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID823	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID824	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID825	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID826	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID827	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID828	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID829	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID830	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID831	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID832	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID833	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID834	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID835	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID836	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID837	Chirundu	16/12/20	22/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID838	Chirundu	16/12/20	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID839	Chirundu	16/12/20	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID840	Chirundu	16/12/20	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID841	Chirundu	16/12/20	23/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID842	Chirundu	16/12/20	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID843	Chirundu	16/12/20	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID844	Chirundu	16/12/20	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID845	Chirundu	16/12/20	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID846	Chirundu	16/12/20	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID847	Chirundu	16/12/20	23/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID848	Chirundu	16/12/20	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID849	Chirundu	16/12/20	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID851	Chirundu	16/12/20	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID853	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID854	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID855	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID856	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID857	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID858	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID859	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID860	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID861	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID862	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID863	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID864	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID865	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID866	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID867	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID868	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID869	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	-

CHIBTID870	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID871	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID872	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID873	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID874	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID875	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID876	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID877	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID878	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID879	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID880	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID881	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID882	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID883	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID884	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID885	Chirundu	18/2/21	23/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID886	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID887	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID888	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID889	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID890	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID891	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID892	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID893	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID894	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID895	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID896	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID897	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID898	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID899	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID900	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID901	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID902	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID903	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID904	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID905	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID906	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID907	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID908	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID909	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID910	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID911	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID912	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID913	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID914	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID915	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID916	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID917	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-

CHIBTID918	Chirundu	NA	NA	NA	NA
CHIBTID919	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID920	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID921	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID922	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID923	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID924	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID925	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID926	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID927	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID928	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID929	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID930	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID931	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID932	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID933	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID934	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID935	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID936	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID937	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID938	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID939	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID940	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID941	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID942	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID943	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID944	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID945	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID946	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID947	Chirundu	18/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID948	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID949	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID950	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID951	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID952	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID953	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID954	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID955	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID956	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID957	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID958	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID959	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID960	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID961	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID962	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID963	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID964	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID965	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID966	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID967	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID968	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID969	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-

CHIBTID970	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID971	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID972	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID973	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID974	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID975	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID976	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID977	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID978	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID979	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID980	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID981	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID982	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID983	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID984	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID985	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID986	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID987	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID988	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID989	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID990	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID991	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID992	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID993	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID994	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID995	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID996	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID997	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID998	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID999	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1000	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1001	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1002	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1003	Chirundu	19/2/21	27/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1004	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1005	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1006	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1007	Chirundu	NA	NA	NA	NA
CHIBTID1008	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1009	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1010	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1011	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1012	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1013	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1014	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1015	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1016	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1017	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1018	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1019	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	-	+

CHIBTID1020	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1021	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1022	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1023	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1024	Chirundu	19/2/21	28/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1025	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1026	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1027	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1028	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1029	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1030	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1031	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1032	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1033	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1034	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1035	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1036	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1037	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1038	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1039	Chirundu	25/3/21	28/04/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1040	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1041	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1042	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1043	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1044	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1045	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	+
CHIBTID1046a	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1047a	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1048a	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1046b	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1047b	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1048b	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	+
CHIBTID1049	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	+	-
CHIBTID1050	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	+	-
CHIBTID1051	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1052	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	+	-
CHIBTID1053	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1054	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1055	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	+
CHIBTID1056	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	+	-
CHIBTID1057	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1058	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1059	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1060	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1061	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1062	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1063	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1064	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1065	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	+	-

CHIBTID1066	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	+	-
CHIBTID1067	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1068	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	+
CHIBTID1069	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1070	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1071	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1072	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	+	+
CHIBTID1073	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	+	-
CHIBTID1074	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1075	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1076	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1077	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1078	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	+	-
CHIBTID1079	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	+	-
CHIBTID1080	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	+	-
CHIBTID1081	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	+	-
CHIBTID1082	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	+	+
CHIBTID1083	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/3/21	-	-
CHIBTID1084	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1085	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	+
CHIBTID1086	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1087	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1088	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1089	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1090	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1091	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1092	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1093	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1094	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1095	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1096	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	+	-
CHIBTID1097	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1098	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1099	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	+	-
CHIBTID1100	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1101	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1102	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	+	-
CHIBTID1104	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1105	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	+
CHIBTID1106	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1107	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1108	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1110	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1111	Chirundu	NA	NA	NA	NA
CHIBTID1112	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1113	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1114	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1115	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1116	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	+	-
CHIBTID1117	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1118	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1119	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	+

CHIBTID1120	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1121	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1122	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	+
CHIBTID1123	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	+	+
CHIBTID1124	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	+	-
CHIBTID1125	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1126	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1127	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1128	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1129	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1130	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	+
CHIBTID1131	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1132	Chirundu	25/3/21	5/7/21	-	-
CHIBTID1133	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1134	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1135	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1136	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1137	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1138	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1139	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1140	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1141	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1142	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1143	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1144	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1145	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1146	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1147	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1148	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1149	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1150	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1151	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1152	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1153	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1154a	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1154b	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1155	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1156	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1157a	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1158a	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1159a	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1160a	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1157b	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1158b	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1159b	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1160b	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1161	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1162	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1163	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1164	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	+	-

CHIBTID1165	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1166	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1167	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1168	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1169	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1170	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1171	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1172	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1173	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1174	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1175	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1176	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1177	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1178	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1179	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1180	Chirundu	25/3/21	18/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1181	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1182	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1183	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1184	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1185	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1186	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1187	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1188	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1189	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1190	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1191	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1192	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1193	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1194	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1195	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1196	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1197	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1198	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1199	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1200	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1201	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1202	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1203	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1204	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1205	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1206	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1207	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1208	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1209	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1210	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1211	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1212	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	+

CHIBTID1213	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1214	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1215	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1216	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1217	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1218	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1219	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1220	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1221	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1222	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1223	Chirundu	25/3/21	19/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1224	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1225	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1226	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1227	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1228	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1229	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1230	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1231	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1232	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1233	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1234	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1235	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1236	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1237	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1238	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1239	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1240	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1241	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1242	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1243	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1244	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1245	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1246	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1247	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1248	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1249	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1250	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1251	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1252	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1253	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1254	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1255	Chirundu	NA	NA	NA	NA
CHIBTID1256	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1257	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1258	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1259	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1260	Chirundu	25/3/21	20/05/2021	+	+

CHIBTID1268	Chirundu	13/05/2021	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1269	Chirundu	13/05/2021	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1270	Chirundu	13/05/2021	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1271	Chirundu	13/05/2021	20/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1272	Chirundu	13/05/2021	20/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1273	Chirundu	13/05/2021	20/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1274	Chirundu	13/05/2021	20/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1275	Chirundu	13/05/2021	20/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1276	Chirundu	13/05/2021	20/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1277	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1278	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1279	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1280	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1281	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1282	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1283	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1284	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1285	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1286	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1287	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1288	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1289	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1290	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1291	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1292	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1293	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1294	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1295	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1296	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1297	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1298	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1299	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1300	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1301	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1302	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1303	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1304	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1305	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1306	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1307	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1308	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1309	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1310	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1311	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1312	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1313	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1314	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1315	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-

CHIBTID1316	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1317	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1318	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1319	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1320	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1321	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1322	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1323	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1324	Chirundu	13/05/2021	27/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1325	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1326	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1327	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1328	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1329	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1330	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1331	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1332	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1333	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1334	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1335	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1336	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1337	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1338	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1339	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1340	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1341	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1342	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1343	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1344	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1345	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1346	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1347	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1348	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1349	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1350	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1351	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1352	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1353	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1354	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1355	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1356	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1357	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1358	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1359	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1360	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1361	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1362	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1363	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-

CHIBTID1364	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1365	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1366	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1367	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1368	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1369	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1370	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1371	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1372	Chirundu	13/05/2021	28/05/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1373	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1374	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1375	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1376	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1377	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1378	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	+
CHIBTID1379	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1380	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1381	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1382	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1383	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	+	-
CHIBTID1384	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1385	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1386	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1387	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	+	-
CHIBTID1388	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	+
CHIBTID1389	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1390	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1391	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	+	-
CHIBTID1392	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	+	+
CHIBTID1393	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	+	-
CHIBTID1394	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1395	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1396	Chirundu	13/05/2021	6/1/21	-	-
CHIBTID1397	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	+	-
CHIBTID1398	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	+	-
CHIBTID1399	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID1400	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID1401	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID1402	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	+
CHIBTID1403	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	+	-
CHIBTID1404	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID1405	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID1406	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID1407	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	+	-
CHIBTID1408	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	+	+
CHIBTID1409	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	+	-
CHIBTID1410	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	+
CHIBTID1411	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	+	-

CHIBTID1412	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID1413	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	+
CHIBTID1414	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID1415	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID1416	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	+	-
CHIBTID1417	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	-
CHIBTID1418	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/8/21	-	+
CHIBTID1419	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1420	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID1421	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1422	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1423	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1424	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	+	-
CHIBTID1425	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1426	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	+	-
CHIBTID1427	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1428	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1429	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	+	-
CHIBTID1430	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1431	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1432	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID1433	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID1434	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	+	-
CHIBTID1435	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1436	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1437	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	+	+
CHIBTID1438	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID1439	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1440	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1441	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	+	-
CHIBTID1442	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	+	-
CHIBTID1443	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1444	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	+	+
CHIBTID1445	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1446	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1447	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1448	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID1449	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID1450	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID1451	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1452	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	+	-
CHIBTID1453	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID1454	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID1455	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	+	-
CHIBTID1456	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1457	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID1458	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID1459	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	+	-

CHIBTID1460	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID1461	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	+	-
CHIBTID1462	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1463	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	+
CHIBTID1464	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1465	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	-	-
CHIBTID1466	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/9/21	+	-
CHIBTID1467	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1468	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	+
CHIBTID1469	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1470	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1471	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	+	+
CHIBTID1472	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	+
CHIBTID1473	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1474	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	+	-
CHIBTID1475	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	+	-
CHIBTID1476	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	+
CHIBTID1477	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	+	+
CHIBTID1478	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	+	-
CHIBTID1479	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	+
CHIBTID1480	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	+	-
CHIBTID1481	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1482	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	+
CHIBTID1483	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	+	-
CHIBTID1484	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	+	-
CHIBTID1485	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	+	-
CHIBTID1486	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1487	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	+
CHIBTID1488	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1489	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	+	-
CHIBTID1490	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1491	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1492	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1493	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	+
CHIBTID1494	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1495	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1496	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1497	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	+
CHIBTID1498	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1499	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1500	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1501	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1502	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1503	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	+	+
CHIBTID1504	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1504(2)	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1505	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1506	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-

CHIBTID1507	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1508	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	+	-
CHIBTID1509	Chirundu	13/05/2021	7/12/21	+	+
CHIBTID1510	Chirundu	1/7/21	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1511	Chirundu	1/7/21	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1512	Chirundu	1/7/21	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1513	Chirundu	1/7/21	7/12/21	-	-
CHIBTID1514	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1515	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1516	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1517	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1518	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1519	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1520	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1521	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1522	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1523	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1524	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1525	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1526	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1527	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1528	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1529	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1530	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1531	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1532	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1533	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1534	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1535	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1536	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1537	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1538	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1539	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1540	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1541	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1542	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1543	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1544	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1545	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1546	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1547	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1548	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1549	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1550	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021		-
CHIBTID1551	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1552	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1553	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1554	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	+	-

CHIBTID1555	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1556	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1557	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021		-
CHIBTID1558	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1559	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1560	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1561	Chirundu	1/7/21	13/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1562	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1563	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1564	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1565	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021		+
CHIBTID1566	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1567	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1568	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1569	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1570	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1571	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1572	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1573	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1574	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1575	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1576	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1577	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1578	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1579	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1580	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1581	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1582	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1583	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1584	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1585	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1586	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1587	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1588	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1589	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1590	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1591	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1592	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1593	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1594	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1595	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1596	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1597	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1598	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1599	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1600	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1601	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1602	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	+	-

CHIBTID1603	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1604	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1605	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1606	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1607	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1608	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1609	Chirundu	1/7/21	15/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1610	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1611	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1612	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1613	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1614	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1615	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1616	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1617	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1618	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1619	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1620	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1621	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1622	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1623	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1624	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1625	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1626 (1)	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1626 (2)	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1627	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1628	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1629	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1630	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1631	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1632	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1633	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1634	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1635	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1636	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1637	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1638	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1639	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1640	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1641	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1642	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1643	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1644	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1645	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1646	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1647	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1648	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1649	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-

CHIBTID1650	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1651	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1652	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1653	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1654	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1655	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1656	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1657	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1658	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1659	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1660	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1661	Chirundu	NA	NA	NA	NA
CHIBTID1662	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1663	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1664	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1665	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1666	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1667	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1668	Chirundu	1/7/21	19/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1669	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1670	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1671	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1672	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1673	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1674	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1675	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1676	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1677	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1678	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1679	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1680	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1681	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1682	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1683	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1684	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1685	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1686	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1687	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1688	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1689	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1690	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1691	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1692	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1693	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1694	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1695	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1696	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1697	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-

CHIBTID1698	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1699	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1700	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1701	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1702	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1703	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1704	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1705	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1706	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1707	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1708	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1709	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1710	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1711	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1712	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1713	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1714	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1715	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1716	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1717	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	+
CHIBTID1718	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1719	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1720	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1721	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1722	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1723	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1724	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1725	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1726	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1727	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	+
CHIBTID1728	Chirundu	1/7/21	20/07/2021	+	-
CHIBTID1729	Chirundu	1/7/21	21/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1730	Chirundu	1/7/21	21/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1731	Chirundu	1/7/21	21/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1732	Chirundu	1/7/21	21/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1733	Chirundu	1/7/21	21/07/2021	-	-
CHIBTID1734	Chirundu	1/7/21	21/07/2021	+	+

Chirundu and Magweto sites : AstV prevalence

Chirundu and Magweto sites : AstV, CoV and co-infection prevalence

Astrovirus phylogenetic tree